

THE IMPORTANCE OF CALCIUM FOR TEETH

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Abstract: Everyone knows that calcium is very useful for tooth enamel. Therefore, we have been told about the benefits of milk since childhood. You need to know in which products and in what amount this important trace element is contained for the body.

Key words: Where is the most calcium, calcium, teeth.

The importance of calcium

With a low calcium content, the tooth enamel becomes very brittle, and even with weak exposure, it can be damaged. The enamel becomes thin and very susceptible to the harmful effects of food acids. The result may be caries and tooth decay.

It is very important to get the necessary amount of calcium from early childhood, at the time of the appearance of the very first teeth. Then the saturation of the tooth enamel with calcium affects the health of permanent dental units.

Calcium is important not only for oral health. This trace element affects the nervous system, the structure of the muscular and skeletal systems.

The daily intake of calcium on average ranges from 800 mg to 1200 mg. Why do the indicators fluctuate so much?

A man needs 200 mg more calcium than a woman.;

for a woman during pregnancy, the norm increases to 1,500 mg;

in the last months of pregnancy, as well as during lactation, the female body requires up to 2000 mg of calcium;

with an active lifestyle and regular exercise, the need for calcium reaches 1400 mg.

A lack of calcium in the diet of children can lead to the formation of enamel with poor acid resistance, while the risk of caries increases significantly.

Therefore, be sure to include foods rich in calcium and vitamin D in the child's diet: dairy products, especially cottage cheese and hard cheese, egg yolk, butter.

"Vitamin and mineral complexes can become an additional source of calcium in children, especially with milk intolerance," says Kuznetsova, "but they should be taken after consulting with a pediatrician."

How to keep calcium in your teeth?

For most children and adults, to prevent dental caries, it is enough to regularly and correctly take care of the oral cavity, use toothpastes and rinses with a remineralizing effect (fluoride-containing, calcium-containing), limit the consumption of sweets and regularly, at least twice a year, visit the dentist.

If necessary, the dentist can prescribe calcium-containing products for topical use at home, which are applied to the surface of the teeth after they are cleaned of plaque. Or to carry out a course of applications with calcium—containing drugs — remineralizing therapy - in a dental office.

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Where is the most calcium? For many, cheese, milk, and yogurt are the main dietary sources of calcium. Also, foods with its high content include canned sardines and salmon with soft bones, sprats, soybeans, beans, and some green vegetables such as parsley and dill. The absolute leader in the content of this trace element. Calcium is an important component of the hard tissue and enamel of teeth. To keep it in your teeth, you need to eat foods rich in it from childhood, take care of your teeth and do not forget to visit the dentist.

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